

DIDACTIC FOUNDATIONS OF IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGICAL TRAINING OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS BASED ON THE STEAM EDUCATION APPROACH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13884665>

Abstract. *Developed research abilities of children become the key not only to successful mastering of all modules of the STEM education program, but also ensure achievements in mastering academic subjects. At the same time, the educational module "Experimentation with living and inanimate nature" finds a direct continuation in the educational module of primary general education "Research activity", which ensures the formation of such research abilities of children as: the ability to see problems, ask questions of different types, formulate a hypothesis, define concepts, classify, collect and analyze information from various sources, observe, conduct an experiment, draw conclusions and inferences, defend the results of the study.*

Keywords: *STEM education, modern education, development of education, teachers, psychologists, technologies, Scientific and technical creativity.*

Modern education is increasingly focused on the formation of key personal competencies, on the development of students' abilities to independently solve problems, on improving their skills in operating with knowledge, on the development of their intellectual abilities. This determines the goal of implementing the partial modular educational program "STEM education of preschool and primary school children": development of intellectual abilities of preschool and primary school children by means of STEM education.

The program "STEM education of preschool and primary school children" (authors S.A. Averin, T.V. Volosovets, V.A. Markova), to which these methodological recommendations relate, is a partial modular program of preschool education aimed at developing intellectual abilities in the process of cognitive activity and involvement in scientific and technical creativity. The program can also be successfully used in extracurricular activities within the framework of the main educational program of primary general education, and each of its sections - educational module - can be independently used both in educational organizations of the above levels and in the system of additional education [2].

Intelligence is understood as a person's ability to think and make decisions. Human intellectual abilities include many components that are interconnected and are realized in the performance of various social roles by a person. It follows from this that the very concept of "intelligence" is closely related to the concept of "ability". Abilities in general are individual personality traits that are subjective conditions for the successful implementation of a certain type of activity.

A look at the history of STEM. In the 17th century, John Amos Comenius (1592-1670) introduced the term "traditional teaching". He organized school education, introduced the concept of the classroom system, the school year and its division into academic quarters, determined how to organize the school day, theoretically developed the classroom system and applied it in practice.

Traditional education has the following features: - in traditional education, strict types of lessons are chosen for all subjects; - knowledge, skills, and competencies on the subject of the lesson are formed and strengthened; - new topic is explained, strengthened, control, assignments are given; - learners are limited to listening to the teacher and mastering, completing the assigned tasks; - each teacher uses the modules and algorithms of the lesson in accordance with the method he uses; - traditional education covers the general range of subjects without direct attention or going deeper into some selected parts.

A traditional curriculum lecture involves the teacher talking about a topic in class, the students taking notes, and then applying the knowledge gained in a test or exam. For certain individuals, traditional classroom structures and lectures can be monotonous, causing learners to quickly lose focus [3].

STEM education was first developed in America at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT). The slogan of this famous institute is "Mind and hand". MIT has developed STEM courses and even created STEM education centers on some campuses. It is widely used in the educational system of Australia, Great Britain, Israel, Canada, China, Singapore, and the USA [5].

The goal of education is to develop students' creative thinking and teach them to use science, technology, engineering, mathematics and art effectively through design-based teaching. STEM education has the following characteristics: □ STEM education relies on binary activities, projects, educational research. □ Knowledge retention is important in a STEM educational environment, but how learners apply that knowledge is even more important. STEM aims not only to educate the learner about a subject, but also to show the student how to apply this subject to real life and how it should be used in the future. For example, a traditional math course may teach a student an equation, but the learner may not know how to apply the equation to real-life situations.

An attempt to develop intellectual abilities in regulated classes in kindergarten and lessons in primary school is ineffective, since higher levels of competence require independence, responsibility in solving non-standard problems, which is poorly achievable within the framework of the traditional learning model. Only a fundamentally new design of the educational environment, an integral part of which is a developing subject-spatial environment, can answer this question. The abbreviation STEM is deciphered as follows: S - science, T - technology, E - engineering, and M - mathematics. Translated from English, these are: natural sciences, technology, engineering art, mathematics. That is why today STEM technology is developing as one of the main trends. STEM education is based on the use of an interdisciplinary and applied approach, as well as on the integration of all four areas of knowledge into a single system [6].

Benefits of STEM education: 1. Integrated learning by topics, not by subjects. STEM education combines interdisciplinary and project-based approaches, which are based on the integration of natural sciences and technology, mathematics and engineering creativity, etc.

2. Application of scientific and technical knowledge in real life. During practical classes, children are clearly demonstrated the possibilities of applying scientific and technical knowledge in real life. In each lesson, as part of a specific project, children design, build and develop products that are "in tune" with those produced by modern industry, thus creating prototypes of a real product.

3. Developing critical thinking and problem-solving skills. STEM learning programs develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills needed to overcome difficulties that children may encounter in everyday life.

4. Developing self-confidence.

Children, creating different products - building bridges and roads, launching airplanes and cars, testing robots and electronic games, developing their underwater and air structures - make and try, refine and test again, thus improving their product. Thus, solving all the problems on their own, they reach the goal. Each victory strengthens their confidence in their abilities.

5. Active communication and teamwork.

STEM programs are distinguished by the need for active communication and teamwork. At the discussion stage, a free atmosphere is created for discussions and expressing opinions, while children are not afraid to express any opinion, they learn to reason and present their own point of view. Children spend most of their time in class developing and testing the created products, being in constant communication and interaction with both teachers and members of their team, within which cooperation is expected related to the distribution of roles, functions, individual actions and materials.

6. Developing interest in technical disciplines.

The goal of STEM education in preschool age is to create conditions for developing children's interest in natural sciences and technical disciplines.

Cognitive interest is associated with a positive emotional attitude to the subject being studied, with the creation of a situation of success, with self-expression and affirmation of child's personality. Classes using STEM technology are exciting and dynamic, emotionally positive. By building rockets, cars, bridges, skyscrapers, creating their own electronic games, factories, logistics networks and submarines, children show an increasing interest in science and technology.

7. Developing motivation for technical creativity through children's activities taking into account the age and individual characteristics of each child.

Despite the rapid growth in the number of children's robotics centers and the introduction of ICT technologies into education at all levels, there are practically no methods that, based on play and other types of children's activities, would ensure the development of engineering and natural science competencies in children, starting from early preschool age. The main drawback: children who begin to study robotics do not have a sufficiently formed understanding of basic mathematical concepts, about the world; cognitive activity in preschool age was not based on a systematically organized experience of experimentation in research activities. Robotics is given as a continuation and development of only design and experimentation with electronic devices. The picture of the world is formed without relying on child's experience in the natural environment and does not turn out to be complete.

In the program "STEM education for children of preschool and primary school age" the world around the child is studied through play and experimentation with objects of living and inanimate nature. Methodological materials provide a connection between living beings and robots, motivating the child to move from play and children's experiment through construction and fascinating technical and artistic creativity to the design and creation of robots - models resembling objects of the living world. The basics of programming and the use of sensors lead the child to the desire to endow these creations with vision, hearing and logic. This is a very exciting process that

can become a motivational core until the end of education and obtaining a favorite specialty: engineer, programmer, designer, scientist [6].

8. Introduction to the world of professions and labor education. According to various statistics, in the near future, 10 leading technical specialties - chemical engineers, software developers, oil and gas engineers, computer systems analysts, mechanical engineers, civil engineers, robotics engineers, nuclear medicine engineers, underwater structure architects and aerospace engineers, specialists in genetic engineering, big data, artificial intelligence, city farming, neurotechnology - will be predominantly focused on STEM knowledge.

9. Preparing children for technological innovations. STEM education prepares children for a technologically advanced world. Over the past 60 years, technology has made a significant leap in development: from the discovery of the Internet (1960) and the advent of GPS technology (1978) to DNA scanning and the widespread use of tablets and smartphones [7].

It is impossible to imagine our world today without technology. This also suggests that technological development will continue, and STEM skills are the basis of this development.

10. The possibility of including STEM technologies in the variable part of the main educational program (MEP). In the main educational program for preschoolers, especially in the part developed by participants in educational relations, the really popular content that meets the interests and priorities of a modern preschooler is implemented in a mobile and dynamic manner. The partial modular program "STEM education of preschool and primary school children" allows you to determine the content and organization of the educational process in the variable part of the main educational program, as well as in studio and club activities of preschool educational organizations and in extracurricular activities of primary school.

Structurally, the partial modular program "STEM education for preschool and primary school children" is presented in the integration of educational modules indicated in the table:

Educational module "Didactic system of Friedrich Froebel" <input type="checkbox"/> Experimentation with objects of the surrounding world; <input type="checkbox"/> Mastering mathematical reality through actions with geometric bodies and figures; <input type="checkbox"/> Mastering spatial relationships; <input type="checkbox"/> Designing in different angles and projections.				
Educational module "Experimentation with living and inanimate nature" - formation of ideas about the surrounding world in experimental activities; - awareness of the unity of all	Educational module "Lego - construction" - ability for practical and mental experimentation, generalization, establishment of cause-and-effect relationships, speech planning and speech commentary on	Educational module "Mathematical development" - comprehensive solution of mathematical development problems taking into account the age and individual	Educational module "Robotics" - development of logic and algorithmic thinking; - formation of programming basics; - development	Educational module "Cartoon Studio "I create the world" - mastering ICT and digital technologies; - mastering media technologies;

<p>living things in the process of visual-sensory perception; - formation of environmental awareness; - analysis of automation processes of farms</p>	<p>the process and result of one's own activity; - ability to group objects; - ability to demonstrate awareness in different areas of life; - fluency in the native language (vocabulary, grammatical structure of speech, phonetic system, elementary ideas about semantic structure); - ability to create new images, fantasize, use analogy and synthesis; - ability to create structures and model objects based on the groove fastening of parts.</p>	<p>characteristics of children in the following areas: size, shape, space, time, quantity and counting.</p>	<p>of design and modeling abilities; -information processing; - development of the ability to abstract and find patterns; - ability to quickly solve practical problems; - mastering the ability to emphasize, schematize, type; - knowledge and ability to use universal sign systems (symbols); □ development of abilities to evaluate the process and results of one's own activities.</p>	<p>- organizing productive activities based on the synthesis of artistic and technical creativity</p>
<p>Implementation of educational modules in priority activities of preschool children: -play; - construction; - cognitive research activities; - various types of artistic and creative activities.</p>				
<p>Each module has a range of specific tasks, which, when comprehensively solved, ensure the implementation of the goals of STEM education: development of intellectual abilities in the process of cognitive research activities and involvement in scientific and technical creativity of preschool children.</p>				

Knowing the age dynamics of the formation of intellectual abilities, through the modeling of intellectually developing situations, the inclusion of children in various types of research activities and scientific and technical creativity aimed at developing and enriching the invariant intellectual structures of the individual, improving the methods of research activities of preschool and primary school children based on the disclosure and formation of individual styles of intellectual activity, the teacher creates conditions for the development of a personality ready for life in modern realities. At the same time, STEM education is a public tool and one of the main conditions.

The conditions for the development of intellectual abilities in the program are provided in accordance with the age and individual characteristics of the child. Starting with sensory perception, through visual-figurative and verbal-logical thinking (educational modules "Didactic System of Friedrich Froebel", "Mathematical Development", "Experimentation with Living and Inanimate Nature"), prerequisites are created for scientific and technical creativity of children, in the process of which they acquire and apply knowledge of algorithms, design and programming and carry out project activities ("Lego Construction", "Cartoon Studio "I Create the World", "Robotics"). The actions of an adult are aimed at ensuring that the child accepts the general scheme of action, feels the connection between the educational modules, the meaning of each link in the general system of action, the hierarchy of secondary and main goals. In this case, the child develops the ability to act "in the mind", which is the most important condition for the development of intellectual abilities [8].

STEM education teaches the student about the mathematical equation and how it can be used in various fields such as science or engineering; - STEM education is aimed at attracting attention, going deeper into all parts of the chosen subject, covering not the general subject, but a part of it; - STEM education engages learners in activities that can be directly applied to the subject, resulting in increased learner interest and bridging the gap; - STEM education does not have one template, the lesson should be focused on child's personality;

STEM - teaching in the educational process envisages the individualization of the educational process by choosing certain subjects and the level of their study, taking into account the interests and characteristics of students. The STEM educational program includes extracurricular and practical activities based on the interests of students. The educational goals of the curriculum should correspond and respond to the interests and requirements of the society and the state. At a time when the position of our independent republic in the world community is growing, international relations, trade, tourism and cultural and economic relations between the countries are developing and strengthening, careful teaching of foreign languages and communication with foreigners to the youth who create its future, to be able to freely discuss issues related to oneself, to teach communication in general orally or in writing is one of the most important tasks of today.

STEM education relies on practical, educational and developmental goals for learners in schools:

The practical goal is to create a model by forming skills and abilities such as understanding, expressing one's opinion, and implementing them within the framework of the requirements noted in the science programs. The educational goal is to develop the thinking of students and develop their acquired knowledge in the process of in-depth teaching of subjects.

The educational goal is to create mental work, qualifications and skills in students, as well as to educate them in the spirit of patriotism and moral purity, to form a comprehensively developed, highly spiritual, independent thinking person, honest to other people, having respect for its values, faith, friendship, self-worth and willpower[11].

The developmental goal represents the development of the learner into a mature person in all respects, that is, the development of his intellectual, emotional and inspiring qualities. The practical, educational and developmental goals of STEM education direct independent learning not only during the course of the lesson, but also outside of the lesson. The transfer of interdisciplinary knowledge, deep thinking, the development of student thinking, research, critical learning, and the use of interactive strategies are taken into account when creating the STEM education curriculum and program. Students, teachers, practical trainers work in STEM education. In a STEM education program, practical activities are based on the integration of one, two or more areas: science, technology, engineering, mathematics and art, depending on the interest of the learner. The teaching process in this integration depends on teacher's style (questionnaire, individual interview, collaborative work, etc.) [10].

A knowledge transfer framework is a framework that aims to demonstrate the interconnectedness of disciplines to understand the complex issues of the present and future. In this, concepts, methods and approaches of several disciplines and fields are taken into account, not only within one discipline. The system of knowledge transfer implies the correct use of pedagogical technologies to develop high-level thinking strategies, creativity and learning of learners. In particular, the use of verbs used in the "Bloom's taxonomy" strategy is important.

Thus, at the current stage of development of education of preschool and primary school children, the emphasis is shifting to the development of the child's personality in all its diversity: curiosity, determination, independence, responsibility, creativity, ensuring the successful socialization of the younger generation, increasing the competitiveness of the individual and, as a consequence, society and the state.

Such knowledge remains for life, since the child does not just listen to adult's story, but observes the process himself, participates in it, experiences it emotionally, makes assumptions, sees the result. In connection with the above, the goal of the educational module "Experimentation with Living and Inanimate Nature" is to educate preschool children about the ecological culture in an interesting and exciting form - experimental activities. A properly equipped research laboratory in the conditions of an educational organization, when correctly introduced into the educational process, gives teachers the opportunity to saturate classes in kindergarten with experiments with living and inanimate nature, awaken children's interest in experimental activities, and form initial skills for conducting independent research.

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